

Efficacy Of Ict-Based Intervention Package On Thirukkural In Developing Moral Values Among Children With Special Needs

Dr. K. Sambath Rani, K.Alagumani

Head of Department of Special Education, Scholar

Abstract

Introduction: This study aimed to evaluate the ICT -based intervention package on Thirukkural in developing moral values among children with special needs. The research was conducted across three special schools and two inclusive schools in coimbatore. This research involved 32 samples of children aged 6-13 yrs, selected through purposive sampling method. Quasi- experimental design was used in the study to evaluate the impact of the intervention on moral values such as worship of god, the blessing of rain, the greatness of Aesthetics, possessions of love and utterance of pleasant words. **Methods:** Research conducted at three intersections such as Locality, Gender, Type of Disabilities. Here we have used t-test to get the result by comparing the pre-test and post-test of the findings. **Result:** Through pre and post test we have concluded that there is a significance difference in terms of Locality, Gender and Types of disabilities. **Recommendations for further research:** Researcher should conduct similar studies with larger size for more generalized results and perform longitudinal studies with more samples and to increase the the reliability and effectiveness. In addition researcher should to extend research to various types of disabilities.

Keywords:

Visual impairment, moral values, ICT based intervention package.

Introduction:

Moral values are the guiding principles of our life and that shapes our decisions, actions and our personality. It make us to be a good human being as in and out. And Thirukkural is one of the greatest tamil precious book, which insists about humanity, equality and things to follow to become a good human being. However, there are no studies that have developed the moral values of special children through Thirukkural by using ICT package. In early stages moral values are inculcated through only oral stories to the children with special needs, there is no adaptations or any modifications done to explain for them. But now in technologized world anything is possible in order to reach the special children and make them learn easily and interstingly. So we have developed a intervention package on teaching moral values through Thirukkural for children with special needs were developed by the researcher. Here some of the literature reviews shows that ICT tools made a great impact among students.

Anbuchelvan and solayan(2005): Examined the effect of using audiovisual equipment on reading-writing communication among standard V students. Results showed significantly better performance in reading and writing communication among students in the experimental group compared to the control group. **Natarajan & Natesan (2004):** Investigated the effectiveness of competency-based teaching of environmental science through video cassettes on students' attainment at the primary level. Results showed significant improvement in students' understanding of environmental science concepts through video-based instruction. **Dr. Alka Jain (2014)** studied the rediscovery of a six-factor entrepreneurial decision-making (EDM) model in Thirukkural, aiming to explore management techniques in ancient India. The research involved analyzing Thirukkural for relevant management techniques and comparing

them with modern entrepreneurship theories. Findings indicated the relevance of Thirukkural's management model in contemporary business environments, emphasizing the importance of planning and risk assessment in entrepreneurship. **Ajantha Devi & Dr. S. Santhosh Baboo (2014):** using OCR in digitizing tamil texts, facilitating accessibility and analysis of printed documents.

Therefore , as far as the researchers can determine and explored only at accessibility , effectiveness of multimedia tools in teaching, through Thirukkural people get management skills. But, the unexplored areas are ICT intervention package on Thirukkural in developing moral values among children with special needs.

Methods:

In order to assess whether there were differences in students moral values through Thirukkural, the researcher collected data at two special schools and three inclusive schools at three categories. Such as, Locality, Gender and Type of Disabilities. The names of the institutions were:

1. Govt. Blind school, Uliyampalayam
2. Red Cross school for speech and hearing, Coimbatore
3. Avinashilingam Higher secondary school for girls, Coimbatore
4. Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya TAT Kalanilayam Middle School, Coimbatore
5. Sri Ramakrishna Vidyalaya Gurukulam Matriculation higher secondary School, Coimbatore

Here the researcher used purposive sampling method to select children with special needs between 6-13 yrs as sample for their study. The sample chosen for the study consists of 32 children with special needs.

Table gives the distribution of the sample

Name of the school	Number of children	Boys	Girls
Special schools			
Govt. Blind school, Uliyampalayam	7	3	4
Red Cross school for speech and hearing, Coimbatore	10	8	2
Inclusive schools			
Avinashilingam Higher secondary school for girls, Coimbatore	3	0	3
Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya TAT Kalanilayam Middle School, Coimbatore	6	6	0
Sri Ramakrishna Vidyalaya Gurukulam Matriculation higher secondary School, Coimbatore	6	6	0

In the research, the researcher made 5 independent variables and 1 dependent variable. Here the researcher aimed at enhancing moral values through Thirukkural ICT based intervention package among children with special needs.

The main independent variables are:

Variables	Levels
Age	6-13yrs
Gender	m/f
Nature of disability	Hearing impaired Visual impaired
Standard	5-8
Locality	Rural/ urban

The main dependent variables included in the study is,

1. Moral values

Here the researcher followed the Quasi- experimental method to get the data within a particular time.

Quasi- experimental design as that in natural social settings in which the research person can introduce something like experimental design into his scheduling of data collection procedures .(Wikipedia, 2002).

The researcher took the need and the importance on moral values as studied, analysed and the components on moral values were identified. For this purpose the researcher had a through discussion with a specialist in the field of special education.

Table shows tha the moral values and their sub- values

Moral values	Sub values
Worship of god	Value of god in comparison to tamil Alphabet
The blessing of rain	Advantages and dis advantages of rain
The grate ness of Asthetics	Respect towards elder
Possession of love	Being caring, lovable towards others Greedy free
Utterance of pleasant words	Speak pleasant words towards others

For each moral value and its components, stories related to those values were narrated to the students, In terms of visuals, pictures, and in sign language.

To findout the effectiveness of ICT based Thirukkural intervention package on the variables, the investigator developed the following tools.

1. Personal data schedule
2. Checklist to assess the moral values

FIGURE I
CONSTRUCTION OF TOOL

**FIGURE II
INTERVENTION USING ICT TOOL**

ICT BASED INTERVENTION TOOL USED IN IMPARTING MORAL VALUES FOR CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

The tool consists of four divisions,

1. The first division consists of choose, for each correct response a score of 1 will be given and for wrong response 0 mark will be given.
2. The second division consists of fillups, for each correct response a score of 2 will be given and for wrong response 0 mark will be given.
3. The third division consists of short answers, for each correct response a score of 2 will be given and for wrong response 0 mark will be given.
4. The fourth division consists of comprehension, for each correct response a score of 5 will be given and for wrong response 0 mark will be given.

The researcher conducted the study in six phases, in integrated and special schools.

Phase I

In the first phase, demographic details were collected.

One month was allocated for the collection of demographic details of the sample.

Phase II

In the second phase checklist were developed and the ICT based intervention package was developed. The tools were prepared to assess the pre- existing knowledge on moral values.

Two months was taken to prepare the tool and intervention package.

3.8.2.1 Intervention package

Ten Thirukkural were selected and for each kural, its meaning and its description were given in terms of,

- Pictures
- Videos
- Audio
- Sign language along with oral presentation

Phase III

In phase III pre- test was conducted, with the developed checklist to assess the existing knowledge on moral values.

Phase IV

In phase IV, the intervention was given for about 3 months. Initially the raport was created among the students, and the videos were played for them to understand and learn the corresponding moral values one by one individually, till they learn the values completely.

Phase V

In 5th phase, post test was conducted for about one month, by administrring the same tool.

Phase VI

Finally the collected data were analysed stastically.

Results:

To assess the impact of ICT based intervention package on Thirukkural in developing moral values among children with special needs, the researcher did the pre and post test and concluded the results by using the SPSS statistical analysis software and t- test were used to determine the

results.

Pre and Post mean scores on moral values with respect to Gender

Variable	Level	Testing	N	Df	Mean	SD	T
Moral values (Gender)	Male	Pre-Test	19	18	14.6842	2.76993	19.49*
		Post-Test			24.6842	1.94515	
	Female	Pre-Test	13	12	15.5385	2.33150	17.30*
		Post-Test			25.6923	2.46254	

The table reveals that the t-value for male ($t=19.49^*$) and female ($t=17.30^*$) was significantly different between pre and post mean scores at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis stated as “ **There is no significant difference in the acquisition of moral values before and after intervention with respect to gender**” is rejected , this shows that the ICT based intervention had created an impact on the children with special needs in the acquisition of moral values. **This might be because of outside exposure the male children would have learnt better when compared.**

FIGURE

COMPREHENSION OF PRE AND POST TEST MEAN SCORES ON MORAL VALUES WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Pre and Post mean scores on moral values with respect to locality

Variable	Level	Testing	N	df	Mean	SD	T
Moral values (locality)	Urban	Pre-Test	18	17	15.5556	2.66176	12.44*
		Post-Test			24.8889	2.29805	
	Rural	Pre-Test	14	13	14.3571	2.43712	17.99*
		Post-Test			25.3571	2.09788	

The table reveals that the t-value for Urban($t=12.44^*$) and Rural ($t= 17.99^*$) was significantly different between pre and post mean scores at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis stated as “ **There is no significant difference in the acquisition of moral values before and after intervention with respect to locality**” is rejected , this shows that the ICT

based intervention influenced the children with special needs to learn the moral values. **Therefore, the overall understanding capacity of the rural children is higher than the urban children.**

FIGURE

COMPREHENSION OF PRE AND POST TEST MEAN SCORES ON MORAL

VALUES WITH RESPECT TO LOCALITY

Pre and Post mean scores on moral values with respect to type of disability

Variable	Level	Testing	N	df	Mean	SD	T
Moral values (Type of disability)	VI	Pre-Test	17	15	14.4375	2.30850	25.10*
		Post-Test			24.9375	2.20511	
	HI	Pre-Test	15	15	15.6250	2.80179	15.23*
		Post-Test			25.2500	2.23607	

The table reveals that the t-value for VI(t=25.100) and HI (t= 15.238) significantly differs between pre and post mean scores at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis stated as “ **There is no significant difference in the acquisition on moral values before and after intervention**

with respect to types of disability” is rejected . This shows that the ICT based intervention is influenced the children with special needs to learn the moral values. **The overall learning and focusing ability of the Visually impaired children is much greater than the Hearing impaired children, due to lack of vision, they have less distraction that impacted the result.**

FIGURE

COMPREHENSION OF PRE AND POST TEST MEAN SCORES ON MORAL VALUES WITH RESPECT TO TYPE OF DISABILITY

Results in comparison to previous studies:

We compared results from similar yielding studies, that shows that there's ICT based intervention package had created an impact on Thirukkural in developing moral values among children with special needs.

Discussion:

In summary, there is a

- Out of 32 samples in this study, the majority of the samples were found to be congenital.
- The major findings reflected that 80% of the samples included in the study were from urban areas .
- The performance of the participants in this study increased after intervention with respect to gender, locality and type of disability.
- Efficacy of ICT based intervention package on Thirukkural has created an impact in developing moral values among children with special needs.
- There is significant difference in the acquisition of moral values before and after intervention based on gender.
- The ICT based intervention package created an impact on the acquisition on moral values before and after intervention based with respect to locality.
- In terms of type of disability, there is significant difference in the acquisition on moral values.
- With regard to moral values, there is significant difference in pre- test and post-test mean scores among male and female individuals.
- Pre and post test mean scores on moral values pertaining to locality showed that there is significant difference between urban and rural children.
- Regarding pre and post test mean scores in the acquisition of moral values, there's significant difference existed between children with hearing impaired

and visual impaired. Since both oral and sign language mode is used to explain.

5.2.0 Suggestions for further research

The present study suggest the following:

1. Further study can be conducted with a more number of samples so that generalized results can be predicted.
2. Logitudinal intervention can be studied with more samples for perfect reliability and effectiveness.
3. Based on the study, further study can be done for different disabilities.

5.3.0 Recommendations of the study

The recommendations emerging out of the study were listed as follows:

1. A similar study can be replicated with in a large group of samples.
2. The teachers and support serives providers can create awarness on moral values among childre with special needs.
3. The study can be done in other states.

5.4.0 Conclusion

Moral values are very much important for everyone. Especially, children with special needs need to explore such values to lead a disciplined and knowledgeable life, in this dramatic world. Learning moral values, whether through texts like the Thirukkural or through various cultural and educational experiences, serves as a cornerstone in shaping individuals and societies. It offers a profound conclusion, that morality not just a set of abstract principles but

a practical guide for navigating the complexities of life. Through studying moral values, we come to understand that integrity, compassion, honesty, and empathy are not mere virtues to aspire, but essential components of a fulfilling and meaningful existence. These values form the bedrock of ethical behavior, fostering trust, cooperation, and harmony in personal relationships, communities, and broader society. Moreover, learning moral values equips individuals with the tools to confront moral dilemmas with clarity and conviction, empowering them to make ethical decisions even in challenging circumstances. Through this process of moral learning the individuals develop a strong sense of character, grounded in principles that transcend self-interest and contribute to the greater good. Ultimately, the conclusion drawn from learning moral values is that they are not only relevant but indispensable in guiding us towards creating a more just, compassionate, and sustainable world.

“Moral values are not about , what is right and what is wrong, its about how we perceive things among others”

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Contact:

Ph no: 9159188862

Gmail: k.alagumanispledu@gmail.com